

TECHNIQUE OF MANAGING FEELINGS AND EMOTIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific-theoretical features and foundations of methods of managing feelings and emotions. A discussion on Emotion Management styles and its importance is also provided.

Key words: feeling, emotion, dynamic stereotype, ambivalence, stress, paroxysmal feelings, aesthetic feelings, intellectual feelings, affect, volitional qualities.

Introduction.

In the social policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, realizing the national identity, creating harmony between the individual and the society through the assimilation of national and universal values is of great importance. In this regard, our country has all the opportunities for researching the unique individual-psychological characteristics of young people, students' abilities, talents, internal capabilities. After a person is born, first of all, his parents want his child to grow and develop. In the future, he will grow up as a well-rounded generation who will benefit from something in this country based on his capabilities. Currently, the number of the world's population is increasing year by year. Most of the children born have various defects. There are several factors that cause these situations. In particular, it occurs as a result of the deterioration of the ecological situation, mistakes made in marriage, and failure to follow a healthy lifestyle. But by now, the opportunities created by our state have opened a wide path for this type of people. Proper establishment of special schools and inclusive education, the process of providing them with education is being formed to meet the state standards.

As long as a person perceives various things and events in the external environment, he is never completely indifferent to these things. The process of human reflection is always active. The reflection process includes:

- that the person has the ability to satisfy the need;
- participation as a subject in objects that help or resist satisfaction;
- relationships that drive him to knowledge and so on.

Because when a person perceives and reflects various things around him, he has a certain attitude towards these things. For example, if we like some things, that is, if they raise our mood, other things we do not like and spoil our mood and make our heart dull. A person likes some food very much, and he does not like other food at all, or some people like it or others dislike it. In general, a person reacts to everything around him, and his relationships are also reflected. People are not indifferent to what they perceive, see, hear, do, think, and dream about. The same objects, persons, characters, events make us happy, others make us sad, and others arouse our anger and hatred. We feel fear when we are in danger, we feel joy when we overcome an enemy or overcome a challenge. There are various definitions of the

concept of emotion in the literature, including; According to the textbook "General psychology" edited by A. V. Petrovsky, emotion is a small attitude that a person expresses in different ways in relation to what is happening in his life, what he is learning or what he is doing. In M.Vahidov's textbook "Child Psychology", it is said that emotion is the reflection of our inner experiences of things and events in the external world in our minds.

In the dictionary authored by Q. Turgunov, emotion consists of pleasant or unpleasant experiences arising from a person's relationship to things and events in reality, people, and himself. In the textbook "General Psychology" authored by Professor E. Ghaziyev, emotion is used in a person, in the brain of living beings, that is, in the sense of reflecting his relationship to the objects that satisfy the needs of individuals and those that hinder him. As can be seen from the above definitions, emotion is a specific reflection process of our feelings, in which the internal experiences and relationships that arise in us during the reflection process of things and events are reflected. So, emotions do not arise by themselves, but arise in connection with the influence of things and events in the external world. Along with feeling, the concept of emotion is widely used in literature. What exactly is the content of the concept of emotion and how is it related to the concept of feeling? Accordingly, if we explain the meaning of the concept of emotion; including Professor E. Ghaziyev's "General Psychology" textbook, emotion is defined as a specific form of the emergence of a mental process consisting of the expression of feelings and internal experiences, the external symptoms of which are usually clearly manifested. Emotions are pleasant or unpleasant experiences that arise from a person's perception of his attitude to reality, related to his needs and interests. It can be seen from the given definitions that the concept of emotion is a broader concept compared to emotion and covers all aspects of a person's daily life and lifestyle. Emotions are related to the needs, interests and aspirations of a person in terms of their occurrence. For example, feelings related to the satisfaction of a person's organic needs create a feeling of pleasure and satisfaction in a person. Inability to satisfy organic emotions lowers a person's spirit, spoils his mood, causes a feeling of suffering and intolerance. Human emotions are related to their content and forms, social and historical conditions. In the period of social and historical development, human needs change. As a result, more and more new feelings appear in a person, such as spiritual, intellectual and aesthetic feelings. Emotions, like other cognitive processes, are manifested during human activities. For example, in order to create a feeling of hard work, it is necessary to engage in socially useful work for a certain period of time. The feeling that arose during this or that activity affects this activity itself and changes it. For example, there is a huge difference in the productivity of someone who is forced to work and someone who works hard. When a person's mood is happy and his soul is refreshed, his work will be blessed, on the other hand, his hand will not go to work when his tongue is sad, anxious or sad. In this sense, the role of emotion in human life is very large.

Emotion also affects other cognitive processes. For example, when a person's spirit is fresh and happy, his perception is still very vivid, his memory is full of feelings, his thinking is sharp, and his speech is burro. Emotions are a system of signals that indicate that events and things happening in a person are important for a person as a person. In this case, the sense organs are clearly separated from the infinite number of stimuli, some of which merge with each other and merge with the resulting sensation. As a result, it evokes an impression and is preserved in the form of memory images expressed by an emotional name. This can be explained physiologically as follows: certain stimuli become signals of calmness for living

beings. Emotional experiences are manifested as a strengthening of the system of reflexes, which is part of a person's personal experience. This expressive function of emotion is called the impressionistic side of emotion in psychology. The word impressive means impression in Latin. I.P. Pavlov explains the positive and negative qualities of certain feelings and emotional experiences through the destructive dynamic stereotypes formed by the adaptation of living beings to the environment around us. High spiritual emotions found in a person should also have their own neurophysiological basis (such as intellectual, moral, aesthetic emotions). In this regard, academician I.P. Pavlov's theory of dynamic stereotyping is very important. Academician I.P. Pavlov wrote about this: "I think that it is often customary at times of changes in the usual lifestyle, and when one of the remaining occupations is separated from a loved one, the heavy emotions experienced during mental anguish the physiological basis is probably the change of the old dynamic stereotype, its disappearance and the persistent formation of a new dynamic stereotype".

Emotions are an external manifestation of consciousness.

The world of emotions is very wide and diverse. Everyone needs to express their feelings in order to maintain their mental health. The modern world puts on a mask on all people, makes them look like each other, and forces them to treat different situations equally.

Types of emotions:

According to the sign, emotions are divided into:

- positive (joy, happiness, love);
- negative (sadness, disappointment, sense of loss);
- ambiguous, i.e. mixed (jealousy, joy, and aggression).

Positive emotions are what makes life gray and boring. Without positive emotions, people are depressed for years. With these positive emotions, you can experience unpredictable situations, for example, when you receive an unexpected gift or remember that you scored the highest score on an exam (test). In any case, such a feeling should be in your life. Their main criterion is that the number of positive emotions should be greater than the number of negative emotions.

In terms of quality, emotions can be divided into several main types: joy, surprise, pain, anger, disgust, hatred, fear and shame. Each feeling is directly related to the perception of the outside world, that is, the more we interact with the world around us, the more emotions we experience.

What are the consequences of emotions in human life? The consequences of anger and fear are the most harmful. These are the emotions that cause the strongest emotional outbursts, and it is not easy for us to overcome them. Feelings like disgust, hatred and shame do not bring us much joy, but they are safe for our psyche.

A different perspective is to separate suffering because we think of suffering for ourselves, which is a product of our imagination and imagination. So hold on to this statement and take nothing for granted.

Let's talk about mood. What happens when we are in a bad mood? Are you in a bad mood for no reason? Are you curious? If you answered yes to all three questions, then you are prone to mood swings. Let's learn how to control our mood.

Moods are not the same as emotions. First, moods are often less intense and last longer than emotions. And unlike most emotions, moods don't have a specific cause. We cannot say exactly why we are in a good mood or why our hearts are troubled.

So where does the mood come from? Many people think that our daily actions, relationships, successes and failures affect our mood. But this is only part of the truth. Our health, how we sleep, what we eat, and even the time of day determine our mood. That is, mood is an indicator of our physiological state and psychological experience at any time. Our mood is like a thermometer: it reacts to all internal and external changes that happen to us.

Unrepressed anger grows and worsens. Anger does not go away by itself. Any behavior of this type is to some extent an attempt to control your mood.

Ways to check how to control your mood.

Choose the three ways you often use to cheer yourself up:

- listen to music;
- exercise (or walking);
- watching TV;
- eat something;
- call or talk to someone;
- being alone;
- avoiding something that spoils your mood;
- use of humor;
- forgetting your favorite work (favorite activity);
- try to consider the problem from different angles.

Exercise can be one of your favorite ways to beat a bad mood. Research shows that regular exercise is one of the best mood regulators. Even a 10-minute walk can beat cravings and increase activity levels. Other factors that can help you feel better include practicing music, avoiding negative thoughts, telling jokes, and engaging in a hobby or other productive activity.

On the other hand, loneliness, smoking, alcohol, and the desire to eat something help at first, and then can cause serious problems. Talking to your loved one is only a good tool when it is constructive and you are looking for solutions. If it drags you to the depths of emotions and enters nonsense, then it is not good. If you can't find the way right away, don't worry!

How to quickly regulate your emotions.

Here we learned about the types of emotions, mood. Let's talk about ways to relieve emotional stress.

Walking.

If you do not have such an opportunity, change the situation. Go outside and vary the speed of movement (slow down, then add a step) and the width of the steps (change small steps to wider ones). You will soon notice that your nervousness will disappear: the activity of the endocrine system will be normalized, the work of the cerebral hemispheres responsible for mood will increase, and the biochemical processes caused by stress will shift to support physical activity.

If you direct your attention to something other than the problem during the movement - observing nature, pleasant memories or dreams, the result will be achieved faster.

Conclusion: The secrets of controlling feelings and emotions are very easy for this manipulator, but difficult for other people. Because everyone can easily control their emotions. Some people even struggle with that. However, we also spend a lot of effort and energy to control our emotions. It takes determination and will to manage emotions. Because most of the

successful people have high determination and will and quickly achieve their goals. One of these is to set a goal and move towards it independently if the feelings are difficult.

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